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THE TRANSFORMATIVE ROLE OF UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES AND OTHER MEMORY INSTITUTIONS FOR CITIZEN SCIENCE AND OPEN SCIENCE IN THE BALTICS

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The article provides a summary of the study report on “The Transformative Role of University Libraries and other Memory Institutions for Citizen Science and Open Science in the Baltics”, which was conducted during Erasmus+ program second framework strategic partnering project “University libraries strengthening the academia-society connection through citizen science in the Baltics – LibOCS”. The full report and summaries of this report in project partners' national languages are available under project materials collection on Zenodo [HERE](#).

Introduction

Citizen Science (further on – CS) as a part of Open Science ensures the range of options for libraries and other memory institutions (museums, archives) to widen their scope and strengthen their role in support of research and society. The report includes the results of the research done with participating specialists from libraries and other memory institutions, professional researchers, citizen scientists, and volunteers from all Baltic countries (Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania).

The aim of the study “The Transformative Role of University Libraries and other Memory Institutions for Citizen Science and Open Science in the Baltics” was to explore the expansion of the role and involvement of memory institutions (Library, Museum, Archive), particularly libraries in research. First task of the study was to find out the experience of all

three parties involved in the arranging of the scientific projects and activities: professional researchers (further on – researchers), librarians and specialists of other memory institutions (further on – MIS), citizen scientists or citizens engaged in science or volunteers (further on – citizen scientists). The second task was to draw a picture of the whole of the situation and of the understandings living about CS, as well as of the collaboration among the parties involved, especially with libraries.

Both the study of the LibOCS project “Drivers and Barriers of Civic Engagement in Open Science and the Role of University Libraries in the Baltics” and other sources of information were showing there are few CS projects in Baltics with engagement of library specialists (Kaseorg, 2022; Dobрева, 2015; Bite, 2020). Considering the general knowledge that there are other MIS engaged in CS projects, authors of the study decided to widen the range of respondents, and to do the surveys not only among librarians but also among employees of other memory institutions.

There were two surveys run during the study. The quantitative method was chosen to ensure the fast gathering of information in a short period.

Methodology of the first survey

The running of the first survey was assumed significant since there was quite a little specific information about the engaged parties and it was relevant to identify as many CS projects or research activities with civic engagement in the Baltics as possible.

Survey was designed as a semi-structured questionnaire. A semi-structured questionnaire format was chosen because it allows to collect various types of data and gives a broader insight on the respondents' views on the topic (Smyth, 2016). Questionnaire included seven questions with suggested responses and six open questions along with six questions regarding the demographic data of the respondents. The questionnaire was conducted in English. The *QuestionPro* tool was used for designing this survey and collecting data. *Microsoft Excel* was additionally used for data analysis. Content analysis was used as the method of data analysis.

From April to the beginning of July 2022, the first survey was carried out online among the employees of Baltic higher education and research institutions and other memory institutions, as well as other citizens involved with a particular research interest.

The insight into the results of the first survey

Out of 208 questionnaires received in total, 127 were complete and valid for analysis. Out of 127 validated questionnaires, 58% (74) were respondents from Lithuania, 25% (31) from Estonia, and 17% (22) from Latvia. The highest level of response was achieved among memory institutions – most respondents were from libraries - 50% (63), museums - 16% (21), researchers - 21% (27), and citizen scientists - 13% (16); no responses were received from the archive specialists.

The responses show that more than half (53 % or 67 responses) of respondents are informed about the research projects with civic engagement. A similar question was asked about the engagement of MIS. And there almost half (49 % or 62 responses) of respondents answered negatively about being informed about such research projects or activities engaging the MIS.

The conducted questionnaire helped to identify more than 25 research projects and activities involving citizens held in Baltic countries, as well as 7 international initiatives. The biggest part of those activities is related to history, the collection and preservation of national identity, and cultural and historical heritage. The data are mostly similar in all Baltic countries: in Estonia, 10 local projects are running and Estonians participate in 4 international projects, at the same time in Latvia - 12 local projects are identified while no international ones, in Lithuania - 7 local and 6 international ones. However, when reviewing the answers of the respondents in general, it should be concluded that most of the answers provide information about projects and activities involving citizens, but not of a research nature, for example, neighborhood development, research on society in general, digitization projects (with no task for citizens), educational projects, various events, and other general responses.

Respondents were asked to share their associations by responding to the question “Please share your understanding and associations of citizen engagement in research activities or Citizen Science”. While analyzing the responses to this question, the content analysis method was exploited as a result of which the responses were categorized into four thematic groups: research topics, research goals and results, research activities, attitudes and values. So-called associations were mostly bonded with the category of “research activities”, following the “research topics”, and continuing with “attitudes and values”, the least associations were stressed with “research goals and results”.

In order to get a detailed understanding of the ways library staff is usually involved in CS projects, the question was asked, and the responses showed that it can be indeed various. Most common five responses are given below:

- They provide a space and a platform for engaged participants and like-minded people (35)
- They are research or project initiators (29)
- They assist with finding relevant information/theoretical materials (27)
- They organize educational events about the research process and CS options (27)
- They perform as specialists on archiving publications, data and other research results (26)

Methodology of the second survey

The second survey served to discover the experience and views of respondents as participants in CS projects or research activities with civic engagement.

In the second survey, the data on collaboration praxis and options in research activities were gathered. There were three respondent groups drawn out: MIS, researchers, and citizen scientists with experience in research activities or projects. The second survey consisted of three versions of the semi-structured questionnaire (each version adapted for each group of respondents). The questionnaire targeting the MIS had nine questions with suggested responses and nine open questions along with three questions regarding the demographic data of the respondents. The questionnaires each targeting researchers and citizen scientists consisted of eight questions with response options provided and nine open questions along with two questions regarding the demographic data of the respondents. Questionnaires were distributed to all the respondents, who gave the permission to be involved in the next part of the research, as well as to participants of other CS projects. It was disseminated from June to the beginning of September 2022.

As in the first survey, the *QuestionPro* tool and *Microsoft Excel* were used here as well. Content analysis method was used to draw conclusions about open questions.

The insight into the results of the second survey

The respondents of the second part of the study were asked to share their insights and thoughts on collaboration in research projects and activities with the citizens involved.

They were asked to choose the most recently participated in or the most memorable research project or activity with civic engagement and share their experience and opinion.

Altogether there were 60 respondents with fully completed valid questionnaires. In terms of Baltic countries, the responses of the respondents were as follows: Latvia – 52% (31), Lithuania – 28% (17), Estonia – 20% (12). There were quite a similar number of respondents in each group: 39% (23) researchers, 28% (17) MIS, 33% (30) citizen scientists.

Each group of respondents was invited to evaluate their understanding of the concept – Citizen Science. In the responses of researchers, the dominating assessment was ranging from medium to high-level knowledge of the issues while among citizen scientists it was in between weak and good one. The MIS are evaluating their knowledge and conceptual understanding of CS as average in general. By sharing the experience in learned tasks of research projects, the most common were named: the information and data retrieval, including consulting on information quality and its importance in the research process in general; next in the line was the project management, coordination, organization, and communication in fulfilling the various aims and stages of research projects; continuing – an archiving and long-term preservation and access assurance.

Both the researchers and citizen scientists, as well as MIS themselves, were asked to evaluate the performance of the MIS in various tasks during CS projects or research activities with civic engagement. In general, the high-level engagement was pointed out in several directions, learn as follows:

- dissemination of research results,
- archiving publications, data and other research results,
- developing of the online platform for CS projects,
- provision of space for meetings of engaged participants and like-minded people (onsite or online; including technical equipment).

The tasks related to the organization of educational events about the research process and CS participation opportunities and the contribution into the recruitment of citizen scientists were evaluated as medium good. None of the MIS tasks' directions was evaluated as weak. The researchers responded with “yes” - 61% (14) and “I don't know” - 39% (9) when asked whether they would like to cooperate with MIS, and there were no “No” responses. At the same time, citizen scientists responded with “yes” 55% (11), “no” - 10% (2), and 35% (7) with “I don't know”. The MIS themselves are very confident in wanting to collaborate with

“yes” - 76% (13), 6% (1) said that they are not interested in collaboration, while 18% (3) chose the response “I don’t know”.

The MIS admits the contribution of researchers in CS projects is invaluable in promoting a broader and deeper understanding of the scientific methods, research process and research problems, as well as in team building and experiencing new practices in solving global issues. On the other hand, as the negative aspects are drawn out the following: difficult terminology and uncommon concepts as well as the misunderstanding that sometimes people want to do something just for fun. Considering the positive aspects of collaboration with citizen scientists, MIS names the sharing of opinions, perspectives and knowledge, generating ideas on new research problems, gathering of big data, and developing an educated and creative community.

Conclusions and recommendations

The responses received in both questionnaires from the three groups of respondents – MIS, researchers, and citizen scientists – lead to the conclusion that CS is perceived positively, it is closely related not only to support science but also to society's welfare and education.

All three targeted groups of respondents in the Baltic countries express their desire to collaborate with MIS in CS projects and other research activities. Both the researchers and citizen scientists are positive about the contribution of MIS in those research projects they were involved in, demonstrating their high-level professional knowledge and skills, as well as skills that are not closely related to their everyday work. Memory institutions, libraries in particular, are well seen as one of the best providers of space for meetings of engaged participants and like-minded people for research activities. At the same time, the responses given in surveys demonstrate the lack of understanding about the process and essence of CS projects, the parties involved in research, as well as their roles and MIS services in this area.

The answers of the respondents witness that MIS's role in research and CS in particular is expanding with the ability to perform the tasks related to the organization of research projects and activities, the research progress, including data management, community gathering, promotion of knowledge sharing and skills and others. Therefore, it can be concluded that the role of MIS is currently in the stage of transformation and a relatively fresh scope is established.

The results and conclusions of the study allow formulating recommendations for memory institutions to promote this transformation:

- Increase the awareness among MIS about their various roles in research and CS.
- Promote collaboration and exchange of experience among MIS on research projects with civic engagement.
- Encourage the promotion and strengthening of existing professional knowledge and skills of MIS that can be particularly useful in CS projects.
- Create a knowledge base for MIS and others about CS projects' modeling including the skills of communication and civic engagement.
- Create the knowledge base for MIS and others about the research process and research data management.
- Participate in CS projects' promotion.
- Invest in MIS infrastructure and set memory institutions in particular libraries and museums as the best meeting space for the community's most effective teamwork in CS projects.

The conducted research has given a high impact and allowed to generate the following recommendations targeting researchers and citizen scientists:

- The knowledge expansion on CS projects and similar activities with civic engagement would promote the collaboration in research in general and constitute the interest in giving feedback among researchers and society, and vice versa.
- It is crucial for researchers and citizen scientists to be familiar with the range of services offered by libraries and other MIS, and, as required, to engage those institutions in research CS projects.

The results and conclusions of the study have highlighted the significant potential of collaboration among MIS, researchers, and citizen scientists for Open Science and solving global issues as well as developing a knowledge society.

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